

Constraining Dark QCD Parameters with Rivet and CONTUR using LHC Measurements

Daisy Pearce

Supervised by Sukanya Sinha

The University of Manchester

August 2025

1 Introduction

1.1 The Standard Model

The Standard Model (SM) of particle physics is a theoretical framework built from all the particles we have observed so far. It best describes our understanding of the interactions between these elementary particles [1][2]. It is made up of twelve fundamental fermions (six quarks and six leptons) and five fundamental bosons (four force-carriers and the Higgs boson).

The force-carriers (also known as gauge bosons) include the W^\pm and Z^0 bosons, which interact via the weak force, a short-range nuclear force. Another gauge boson is the photon (γ), carrying the electromagnetic force between electrically charged particles. Three of the leptons (electron, muon and tau) carry electric charge, so can interact via the weak and electromagnetic force, whereas their neutral counterparts (electron, muon and tau neutrinos) are electrically neutral so can only interact via the weak force. This is encapsulated within the framework of quantum electrodynamics (QED).

The final gauge boson is the gluon (g), mediating the strong interaction since they carry colour charge. This is described by quantum chromodynamics (QCD), where quarks carry a colour charge (representing a quantum number) which is mediated by the gluon via the strong force [2]. This is analogous to electric charge mediated by the photon for electromagnetism.

The particles that we see as a part of the SM make up the matter (and anti-matter) we observe in the universe today. However, cosmological and astrophysical measurements have concluded that the matter we see is not all the matter that exists, there is approximately five times more dark matter (DM) in the Universe than SM matter [3].

1.2 Dark Matter

Cosmological measurements such as those of the Coma cluster, where the amount of luminous matter does not explain the large Doppler velocities of the individual galaxies within it, have led us toward the theory of DM [4]. How most of the matter in the universe is seemingly undetectable by current research

methods leads to different theories about what it could be.

At the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), researchers have been trying to detect DM through collisions, such as proton-proton collisions. This proves tricky since, similarly to neutrinos, DM is invisible. However we can use its signature, missing transverse momentum, and visible decay particles in the collider to infer the presence of DM [3].

A highly favourable model is Weakly Interacting Massive Particles, known more commonly as WIMPs, due to the ‘WIMP miracle’. It was assumed that if a dark matter candidate (the WIMP) had a mass around the electro-weak scale and be mediated by the weak interaction, then the relic density would be matched to the measured value from cosmology as $\Omega_{\text{DM}}h^2 \approx 0.12$ [5]. This constraint led to specific parameter spaces being researched. Opening up the parameter spaces with other well-motivated models can allow us to probe different areas within these phase spaces [6].

In many other models DM consists of more than one particle [5]. An example of one of these strongly supported models is the dark sector, consisting of an entirely new sector of particles, forces and interactions which weakly interact with SM particles through portal interactions [7][8].

This project focuses on the strongly interacting particles within the dark sector, known as dark QCD.

1.2.1 Dark QCD

Dark QCD is theorised to exist as a part of Hidden Valley models within the dark sector of Beyond the Standard Model (BSM) physics. Theoretically dark quarks exist, carrying dark colour charge mediated by dark gluons via a dark strong force, however coupling with SM particles through a portal or mediator, meaning they are unable to be directly detected [8][5]. These dark quarks then hadronize forming dark hadrons, which can either be stable or unstable (meaning they decay back to SM particles) [8].

Opening up the searches to Hidden Valley models, which include dark QCD, allows the probing of parameter space not originally explored in previous searches. Unique signatures of dark QCD include Semi-Visible Jets (SVJs), on which this project focuses [7].

1.3 Semi-Visible Jets

Quark and gluons cannot exist freely and hadronize to form jets [9]. In particle colliders, if a fraction of these hadrons originating from the parton shower are stable dark hadrons, their missing energy can be aligned along the direction of the jet containing the SM hadrons. These are known as Semi-Visible Jets (SVJs) [8].

The fraction of stable dark hadrons can be calculated as

$$r_{\text{inv}} = \left\langle \frac{\text{no. stable hadrons}}{\text{no. total (stable + unstable) hadrons}} \right\rangle, \quad (1)$$

which essentially acts as a probability of dark hadrons decaying into invisible particles [7]. Hence it can take values in the range 0-1, meaning a value of $r_{\text{inv}} \rightarrow 0$ consisting of unstable dark hadrons decaying to visible states and a value of $r_{\text{inv}} \rightarrow 1$ being fully stable dark hadrons. When attempting to constrain the phase space of r_{inv} , lower values are more favourable since we have a greater understanding of SM particles being detected [7].

1.4 Overview and Model Parameters

In this project we are using simulation data produced in PYTHIA, a general-purpose Monte Carlo (MC) event generator [10]. These simulations are processed through Rivet to replicate the analysis steps performed on ATLAS measurements [11]. This then allows for comparison to be completed using CONTUR, which scans the distributions from Rivet and statistically compares them to SM [12]. We are doing this to narrow down the phase space of the BSM model parameters, since parameter values that are statistically unlikely when compared with real SM data can be excluded [12].

The variables we are going to be altering with our simulations in PYTHIA are the mediator mass, M_{med} and the invisible fraction, r_{inv} [10]. We will be changing M_{med} by 200 GeV intervals within the range 1400-4000 GeV, and r_{inv} will be tested in the range 0.1-0.9 in 0.1 increments.

2 Method and Results

2.1 Using PYTHIA and Rivet

PYTHIA cards (command files for PYTHIA simulation) were created for each combination of our varying parameters as the input files for PYTHIA [13][10]. These then output HepMC (High energy physics Monte Carlo) files which are object oriented event records written in C++ for MC Generators in High Energy Physics [14]. HepMC files are the input files that allow Rivet to analyse and produce YODA (Yet more Objects for Data Analysis) files, which store processed statistical data (primarily histograms) [11][15].

Figure 1: CONTUR exclusion plots with cross-section values taken from HEPData [16]. The (expected) observed exclusion limit at a 95% CL is shown with a (dotted) solid line and at a 68% CL with a dashed line overlaid onto a 2D heat map of CL for varying r_{inv} and M_{med} values (left). The analysis pools that were most sensitive (right). The area under the curve is excluded.

2.2 CONTUR and Producing Plots

For CONTUR to run it requires the YODA files aswell as a param.dat file, which contain the parameters varied only (in our case the M_{med} and r_{inv} values). A Python script was used to create multiple folders

(indexed corresponding to their parameter vales) within a parent directory labelled ‘13TeV’, so CONTUR knows which. It also copied the YODA files into their respective parameter folder. The main directory which the ‘13TeV’ folder is in was labelled as ‘myscan’, which is required for CONTUR to scan all of the data [12].

To complete the scans, we ran CONTUR locally (via Docker) using the command ‘contur -g myscan’ [17]. This produced a ‘contur_run.db’ file, allowing us to create the plots using the ‘contur-plot contur_run.db mYm mXm’ command. Our variable parameters replacing ‘mYm mXm’ were M_{med} and r_{inv} which produced exclusion plots from the data as shown in figure 1.

The 95% CL exclusion limit appears at a mediator mass (M_{med}) of approximately 3000-3500 GeV for all r_{inv} as indicated in figure 1 (left) by the solid line. This provides a high CL that parameters below this may be excluded from searches at this particular cross-section. From this plot we can infer that the most sensitive analysis pool for this exclusion is the ATLAS 13 TeV four-lepton pool, containing ATLAS_2017_I1625109, ATLAS_2019_I1720442 and ATLAS_2021_I1849535 analyses. Hence, for the excluded area, the number of four-leptons observed is close to what is expected from known SM processes, such that there is little room for BSM physics. However, for higher mediator masses, there is a lower cross-section predicting less events. This loss of sensitivity means we are unable exclude these regions of the parameter phase space.

As mentioned earlier, the exclusion remains pretty consistent across all r_{inv} values. The most prominent deviation can be viewed at very high r_{inv} (0.9-1) in figure 1, where the exclusion limit decreases compared to the rest. This is due to the fact that at high r_{inv} , the decays are predominantly to invisible particles, causing the analysis to rely on missing transverse momentum [8]. Consequently, the model will be less sensitive in this region due to the difficulty of distinguishing a potential BSM with the SM background, since neutrinos similarly cause missing transverse momentum [3].

2.3 Experimenting with Cross-Section

Where the cross-section was originally scaled, within the Python script that produced the jobscript files, we rescaled those original values taken from HEPData by factors x0.1 and x0.01 [16]. The same method was used to produce CONTUR plots as in section 2.2. The plots produced for the x0.1 and x0.01 cross-section are shown in figures 2 and 3 respectively.

Similarly to figure 1, figures 2 and 3 have both 68% and 95% CL exclusion limits, heavily excluded by the ATLAS 13 TeV four-lepton pool. However, the scaling of the cross-section causes the exclusion limit to be lowered. Comparing the approximate 2000-2500 GeV and ~ 1500 GeV mediator masses for x0.1 and x0.01 respectively with the 3000-3500 GeV in figure 1 at 95% CL, we see a decrease after each down-scaling of the cross-section. When decreasing the cross-section, we are decreasing the number of events in our model, hence we are less certain on constraining these parameters. Among the four-lepton pool, two other pools were highly sensitive to the scaled cross-section data in figures 2 and 3. Both were ATLAS 13 TeV pools, one being a lepton with missing transverse momentum plus optional jets, consisting of ATLAS_2017_I1614149, ATLAS_2019_I1750330:TYPE=BOTH, ATLAS_2023_I2628732, ATLAS_2018_I1656578 and ATLAS_2018_I1705857 analyses. The other pool was unlike dileptons plus

Figure 2: CONTUR exclusion plots with scaled HEPData cross-section values by a factor $\times 0.1$ [16]. The (expected) observed exclusion limit at a 95% CL is shown with a (dotted) solid line and at a 68% CL with a dashed line overlaid onto a 2D heat map of CL for varying r_{inv} and M_{med} values (left). The analysis pools that were most sensitive (right). The area under the curve is excluded.

Figure 3: CONTUR exclusion plots with with scaled HEPData cross-section values by a factor $\times 0.01$ [16]. The (expected) observed exclusion limit at a 95% CL is shown with a (dotted) solid line and at a 68% CL with a dashed line overlaid onto a 2D heat map of CL for varying r_{inv} and M_{med} values (left). The analysis pools that were most sensitive (right). The area under the curve is excluded.

missing transverse momentum and jets, consisting of ATLAS_2019_I1718132:LMODE=ELMU, ATLAS_2021_I1852328 and ATLAS_2019_I1759875 analyses. Even though these two pools do not constrain the parameter phase space, they are still statistically consistent with the SM background, so the number of events they observed are not inconsistent with our model's predictions in these regions.

3 Conclusions

Rivet and CONTUR have been used to analyse and compare data from the LHC against a dark QCD model with a MC simulation using PYTHIA to constrain a parameter phase space consisting of a mediator mass (M_{med}) and r_{inv} . Exclusion plots were produced, demonstrating the constraints our model exhibits - as well, comparing how these differ when scaling the cross-sections.

We can conclude at higher cross-sections, larger regions of parameter phase space can be excluded within this model. The most sensitive analysis pool was the ATLAS 13 TeV four-lepton pool, providing large coverage in all three figures, with high sensitivity to exclusion, especially for lower M_{med} values. We can also state that changing r_{inv} doesn't have a massive effect overall on exclusion, it's most prominent difference is at very high r_{inv} values.

References

- [1] M. K. Gaillard, P. D. Grannis, and F. J. Sciulli, "The standard model of particle physics," *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, vol. 71, pp. S96–S111, Mar 1999.
- [2] D. Kar, *Experimental particle physics: understanding the measurements and searches at the Large Hadron Collider*. IOP Publishing, 2019.
- [3] A. Boveia and C. Doglioni, "Dark matter searches at colliders," *Annual Review of Nuclear and Particle Science*, vol. 68, no. 1, pp. 429–459, 2018.
- [4] F. Zwicky, "Die rotverschiebung von extragalaktischen nebeln," *Helvetica Physica Acta, Vol. 6, p. 110-127*, vol. 6, pp. 110–127, 1933.
- [5] M. Bauer and T. Plehn, *Yet another introduction to dark matter: the particle physics approach*, vol. 959. Springer, 2019.
- [6] F. Kahlhoefer, "Review of lhc dark matter searches," *International Journal of Modern Physics A*, vol. 32, no. 13, p. 1730006, 2017.
- [7] C. Cazzaniga and A. De Cosa, "Leptons lurking in semi-visible jets at the LHC," *The European Physical Journal C*, vol. 82, no. 9, p. 793, 2022.
- [8] T. Cohen, M. Lisanti, H. K. Lou, and S. Mishra-Sharma, "LHC searches for dark sector showers," *Journal of High Energy Physics*, vol. 2017, no. 11, pp. 1–32, 2017.
- [9] M. Creutz, *Quarks, gluons and lattices*. Cambridge University Press, 1983.
- [10] C. Bierlich, S. Chakraborty, N. Desai, L. Gellersen, I. Helenius, P. Ilten, L. Lönnblad, S. Mrenna, S. Prestel, C. T. Preuss, T. Sjöstrand, P. Skands, M. Utheim, and R. Verheyen, "A comprehensive guide to the physics and usage of PYTHIA 8.3," *SciPost Phys. Codebases*, p. 8, 2022.
- [11] C. Bierlich, A. Buckley, J. Butterworth, C. H. Christensen, L. Corpe, D. Grellscheid, J. F. Grosse-Oetringhaus, C. Gutsche, P. Karczmarczyk, J. Klein, L. Lonnblad, C. S. Pollard, P. Richardson, H. Schulz, and F. Siegert, "Robust Independent Validation of Experiment and Theory: Rivet version 3," *SciPost Phys.*, vol. 8, p. 026, 2020.

- [12] A. Buckley *et al.*, “Testing new physics models with global comparisons to collider measurements: the Contur toolkit,” *SciPost Phys. Core*, vol. 4, p. 013, 2021.
- [13] E. Gillies, “Pythia8 to HepMC to Rivet.” <https://rivet.hepforge.org/rivet-tutorial-18x-gillies.pdf>, 2018. Accessed: August 26, 2025.
- [14] M. Dobbs and J. B. Hansen, “The hepMC c++ monte carlo event record for high energy physics,” *Computer Physics Communications*, vol. 134, no. 1, pp. 41–46, 2001.
- [15] A. Buckley, L. Corpe, M. Filipovich, C. Gutschow, N. Rozinsky, S. Thor, Y. Yeh, and J. Yellen, “Consistent, multidimensional differential histogramming and summary statistics with YODA 2,” *SciPost Phys. Codebases*, p. 45, 2025.
- [16] CMS Collaboration, ““Figure 8c” of “Search for resonant production of strongly coupled dark matter in proton-proton collisions at 13 TeV” (Version 3).” HEPData (dataset), 2022. <https://doi.org/10.17182/hepdata.115426.v3/t71>.
- [17] Docker Inc., “Docker desktop.” <https://www.docker.com/products/docker-desktop/>, 2025. Version 4.43.2, Accessed: July 31, 2025.